

removal of excess of thionyl chloride and benzene under reduced pressure, carbon disulphide (48 ml) and powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.018 mol) were added to the residue and the mixture refluxed for further 3 h and then stored overnight at room temperature. Carbon disulphide was then removed and the complex hydrolysed with ice-cold hydrochloric acid. The product was then extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was successively washed with water, dilute hydrochloric acid, sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) and finally with water, dried and chloroform recovered. Pure cyclic ketone was obtained on crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether.

2,3-Tetramethylene-substituted-5,6-benzocyclohexane: A mixture of cyclic ketone (0.012 mol), diethylene glycol (20 ml), potassium hydroxide (0.048 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (1.7 ml, 80%) was refluxed for 1 h at 130-140°. The condenser was then removed and the internal temperature was slowly raised to 190-5°. The condenser was replaced again and the mixture refluxed for further 3 h. The contents were cooled, acidified with hydrochloric acid, extracted with ether, washed, dried and ether recovered. The residue gave pure hydrocarbon on crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether.

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Preparation of Arylazo-bis-acetoximes

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IN an earlier communication, the preparation of ten new hydroxytriazenes was reported by the authors¹, in view of the importance of this class of reagents in analytical chemistry. The arylazo-bis-acetoximes also have the same chelating moiety as hydroxytriazenes.

Mai² discovered a group of substances conveniently called as arylazo-bis-oximes by coupling diazonium salts (1 mol) with ald- or ket-oximes

(2 mol). Bamberger³ proved that arylazo-bis-oxime have the hydroxytriazene skeleton. Elkins and Hunter⁴ reported preparation of six arylazo-bis-oximes and preparation of their nickel, cobalt, copper and iron complexes. Subsequently, Bhargava and Sogani⁵ reported the preparation of four arylazo-bis-oximes and screened for their utility in gravimetric analysis of copper and nickel.

The present communication describes the preparation of fourteen arylazo-bis-acetoximes and some of their physical properties. Qualitative spot test with α -naphthylamine has also been developed.

Experimental

Freshly prepared acetoxime (2 mol) was dissolved in 10% sodium hydroxide solution and then cooled to 0° by adding some crushed ice to it and kept in ice-bath. A diazotised salt solution of the substituted anilines (1 mol) was then added slowly under mechanical stirring to this solution. The pH was always maintained at ~ 10 and the temperature during the entire course of addition being kept at 0°. The crude compounds obtained are mostly dark coloured. The crude product in each case was washed twice with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) to remove the coloured impurities, and recrystallised from ethanol-water mixture. The physical characteristics of the compounds are summarised in Table I.

Two methods for the spot test detection of hydroxytriazenes were reported by Purohit⁶. The basis of the first test is the formation of pink colour when an acetic acid solution of α -naphthylamine is added to an acetic acid solution of hydroxytriazenes. In the second method, addition of 2 to 5 drops of a saturated ethanolic solution of picric acid to either a pinch of solid hydroxytriazene or a drop of its ethanolic solution gives a pink or red colour of precipitate. Spot test detection of arylazo-bis-acetoxime series of compounds with α -naphthylamine has been developed for the first time. However, with picric acid these have failed to respond to the test.

One drop of arylazo-bis-acetoxime solution in acetic acid (0.001%, w/v) was treated in a small test tube with a drops of acetic acid solution (0.01% w/v) of α -naphthylamine. Pink or reddish brown colour developed immediately. Gentle warming of the test solution further intensified the colour. The test was performed with seventeen arylazo-bis-acetoxime compound. The results of the test are given in Table 1.

Discussion

Hydroxytriazenes are reported to exist in intramolecular hydrogen bonded form (III). This group of compounds have also been named as triazene oxide on the basis of possible existence of its tautomeric form (II).

TABLE I—ARYLAZO-BIS-ACETOXIME COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	Aryl	Colour, shape of crystals	M.p.	Analysis % : Found/Calcd.*			Colour with α -naphthylamine
				C	H	N	
1.	<i>m</i> -Methylphenyl	Reddish brown, tiny	119°	59.10 (59.07)	7.48 (7.63)	20.63 (21.19)	Reddish brown colour on warming and then cooling
2.	<i>o</i> -Carboxyphenyl	White silky, flakes	102°	53.32 (53.05)	6.03 (6.16)	18.76 (19.03)	No action. Test not given
3.	<i>m</i> -Carboxyphenyl	Light reddish brown, tiny	174°	52.88 (53.05)	6.10 (6.16)	18.91 (19.03)	No change in colour. Test not given
4.	<i>p</i> -Carboxyphenyl	Light brown, fine	140°	53.17 (53.05)	5.90 (6.16)	18.68 (19.03)	No change in colour. Test not given
5.	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	Yellow, large rectangular	48°	48.64 (48.80)	5.66 (5.80)	23.61 (23.72)	Light pink colour on gentle warming
6.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	Light brown, needless	50°	48.69 (48.80)	5.72 (5.80)	23.60 (23.72)	Pink colour on warming
7.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	Yellow, needless	69°	48.94 (48.80)	5.69 (5.80)	23.43 (23.72)	Pink colour on warming
8.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl ^a	Brown, fine	111°	51.18 (50.62)	5.95 (6.02)	19.40 (19.68)	Violet red colour on slight warming
9.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl ^b	Dark violet red, small	111°	50.41 (50.62)	5.98 (6.02)	19.52 (19.68)	Immediate pink colour in cold, intensified on heating
10.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl ^c	Black, needles	113°	50.13 (50.61)	5.99 (6.02)	19.21 (19.68)	Immediate pink colour in cold, intensified on heating.
11.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl ^d	Yellow, needles	144°	43.61 (43.78)	5.39 (5.20)	17.61 (17.02)	Red colour on slight warming
12.	<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Violet, tiny	98°	55.89 (55.70)	7.28 (7.19)	19.66 (19.99)	Reddish brown colour on warming
13.	<i>m</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Blackish brown, fine	103°	55.56 (55.70)	6.87 (7.19)	19.63 (19.99)	Reddish brown colour on warming
14.	<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	Shining brown, tiny	139°	55.81 (55.70)	7.02 (7.19)	19.75 (19.99)	Reddish brown colour on warming

*Halogen % : ^aCl, 12.04 (12.44); ^bCl, 12.67 (12.44); ^cCl, 12.13 (12.44); ^dBr, 23.82 (24.27).

It has been observed that arylazo-bis-acetoximes do not give spot tests with picric acid but give a positive spot test with α -naphthylamine. This may be indicative of a greater contribution of hydroxy-triazene form (I) towards the final structure. The negative picric acid test can also be interpreted to mean that the contribution of triazene-oxide form (II) is either altogether absent or is negligible and that arylazo-bis-acetoximes might be existing predominantly in form I.

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Raney Nickel Desulphuration of Cyclic Nitrogen and Sulphur containing Compounds. Desulphuration of 1,2,4-Thiadiazolidines

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RECENTLY, we have carried out the desulphuration studies of certain acyclic thioamido group containing compounds^{1,2} in the presence of Raney nickel (W-2). The present paper describes the Raney nickel desulphuration of certain cyclic thioamido group containing system.

When 5-imino-4-phenyl-3-phenylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (1a) was desulphurated in boiling ethanolic medium in the presence of Raney nickel (W-2), a pale yellow solution was produced. This on removing the solvent, afforded a solid crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 150°. This product neither reduced Fehling's solution nor Tollen's reagent. It formed a hydrochloride, m.p. 137° and a picrate, m.p. 170° by its interaction with cold concentrated HCl and aqueous picric acid, respectively. On reaction with phenyl isothiocyanate it produced 1-(*N, N'*-diphenyl)formamidino-3-phenylthiourea (3a), m. p. 165-66° (Scheme 1).